

ISic1359

Funerary inscription for Kallistos and Eukarpia

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 244

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 28 cm

Width 30.2 cm

Depth 3.5-3.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: 30-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Κάλλιστος καὶ Ε [ύ]
2. καρπία οἱ φιλόστορ
3. γοι ζῶντες ἑαυτοῖς
4. ἐποίησαν καὶ τοῖς
5. ἰδίοις. εἰρήνη πᾶσι

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Kallistos and Eukarpia, who, loving one another tenderly, made this while living for themselves and
their family. Peace to all.

Translation (it)

Callistos e Eukarpia, che, amandosi reciprocamente con tenerezza, in vita la costruirono per se

stessi e per i propri cari. Pace a tutti.

Commentary

The letter forms (e.g. rhomboid shapes and Σ not C for sigma) suggest a date not later than the third century BC; but the final phrase is typical of Christian inscriptions, which implies that this is one of the earliest Christian texts from Catania. Kallistos is a common name, although rare in Sicily; Eukarpia is less common generally, but well attested in eastern Sicily. The paint is a modern addition and misses several of the less well-preserved letter strokes

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Bibliography

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